

1 **Incised stone artefacts from the Levantine Middle Palaeolithic and human**
2 **behavioural complexity.**

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6 **Supplementary Online Material 1**

7 **GIS workflow**

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9 The analysis workflow of the macro surface data processed with GIS tools is adapted
10 from Benito-Calvo et al., 2015, 2018; Caricola et al., 2018; Zupancich et al., 2019;
11 Paixao et al., 2021. In our study, we used Qgis 3.14.1 “Pi” through the following steps:
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13 1. Import surface xyz point coordinates (.csv, .txt, .ascii). Using UTM coordinate
14 projection.

15
16 2. Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

17 a. Create DEM raster, Z coordinate as elevation value (using: TIN Interpolation
18 tool)

19 i. Interpolation attribute: Z

20 b. Fill No Data cell (using Fill nodata Gdal)

21
22 3. Digital Surface Models (DSM) or Terrain analysis computation (TAC)

23 a. Hillshade (Hillshade Gdal)

24 i. Z factor: 1.0

25 ii. Scale: 1.0

26 b. Slope

27 i. Create Slope raster using Slope Gdal (from the generated fill nodata
28 DEM)

29 1. Ratio of vertical units to horizontal: 1.0

30 2. Create Contour polygons (Gdal)

31 a. Interval between contour lines: 10.0

32 b. Offset: 0

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